

ISic0449

I.Sicily inscription 0449

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Ilenia Gradante,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

37.0767995, 15.2848558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 263 + 13069

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25.5 cm

Width 15 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [hicpos]ita · Aurelia
2. [quaevix]it annos
3. [---]III · bene
4. [requies]ce
5. [in pace Se]ratoria

Apparatus

Text of Agnello with suggestions of Ferrua

[in pa]ce Cri(isti), Agnello

(vacat) [Se]ratoria, Agnello; vel [in pace Ma]ratoria, Ferrua

Translation

Commentary

Lower fragment was published by Orsi in 1893; upper fragment by Carini in 1874; Mommsen only aware of upper fragment; Agnello united the fragments,

and Ferrua amended the reading.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491677

EDCS 21900511

Bibliography

Carini, I. 1874. Rassegna archeologica. *Archivio Storico Siciliano*. 2: 506-514. At 510 no.11

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7170 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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Agnello, S.L. 1956. Aggiunte e correzioni alle epigrafi paleocristiane di Siracusa. *Nuovo Didaskaleion*. 6: 52-68. At 55 no.8 fig.1e

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At 33 no.100

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